

Interview Analysis Procedure

To analyze the interviews, we followed a structured and systematic process.

Step 1: Data Extraction and Summarization

The first step involved filtering and summarizing each interview in a tabular format. We used both the interview transcripts and our accompanying notes to extract relevant information. Each row in the table corresponds to one interview, and the columns capture key aspects of the discussion. The columns included:

- ID
- Interviewee
- Company
- Research Start
- Research Method/ Participants
- RAG Use Cases
- RAG Opportunities/Goals
- RAG Challenges
- Lessons Learned
- RAG System (Technology)
- Technological Readiness Level
- Requirements
- Requirements Ranking
- Metrics/Evaluation
- Goals Implemented/Not Implemented
- Future Potential
- Risks

We populated the table with essential background information and a condensed summary of the main points discussed in each interview. This structured approach ensured consistency and made it easier to compare insights across interviews.

Step 2: Categorization of Data

In the second step, we systematically reviewed each column in the interview summary table and identified emerging categories within each. Based on this categorization, we selected four key columns to serve as the foundation for our research questions:

- **RAG Use Cases and Opportunities/Goals**
- **RAG Challenges and Lessons Learned**
- **Requirements and Requirements Ranking**
- **Metrics/Evaluation**

These categories directly informed the development of our research questions, aligning the qualitative data structure with the study's analytical framework.

Step 3: Collection of Cited Statements

For each research question, we extracted relevant statements from the interviews, including verbatim citations with timestamps. These were compiled in separate Word documents, organized by research question. Each document contains a list of categorized statements from participants, providing a clear view of the data supporting each analytical theme.

Step 4: Coding Overview Table

We then applied a color-coding scheme to the statements. Each category was assigned a distinct color, and corresponding segments within the statements were highlighted accordingly. This visual coding allowed us to easily trace which participant made which statement, and to which category it belonged.

Next, we transferred the color-coded data into a structured overview table. In this table, each interview is linked to its associated statements, with color coding retained to indicate the relevant categories. This format provided a clear, visual overview of which categories were emphasized by each interviewee and helped identify patterns across interviews.

Step 5: In-Depth Analysis and Reporting

In the final step, we conducted an in-depth analysis of the categorized statements. We systematically reviewed the data, refined the categorizations, and synthesized the findings in formal written form. This analysis formed the basis of the final paper, summarizing the insights from the interviews and providing a comprehensive answer to the research questions. The result is a coherent overview of the current state of RAG adoption, including key challenges, goals, and evaluation metrics as reported by the participants.

